

THE ROLE OF COOPERATIVE SOCIETIES ON THE WELL-BEING OF STAFF OF PUBLIC POLYTECHNICS IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA.

¹ Agbasi, Obianuju Emmanuela (Ph.D.) and ² Ufoaro Ebele Theresa

Department of Cooperative Economics and Management, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka,
Anambra State, Nigeria. Email: oe.agbasi@unizik.edu.ng

Department of Cooperative Economics and Management, Anambra State Polytechnic, Anambra State,
Nigeria. Email: ufoarohebele@gmail.com

Abstract

This study examined the role of cooperative societies on the well-being of staff of public Polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to investigate the effects of educational loans on the well-being of the staff and to determine the effect of commodity purchase (household assets) on the well-being of staff of public polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria. The total population of this study was three thousand four hundred and fifty eight (3,458) comprising the entire cooperators in the two public polytechnics in Anambra State, namely Federal Polytechnic, Oko, and Anambra state Polytechnic, Mgbakwu. The solvent method was used to collect a sample size of 355 respondents which were further divided among cooperators in the two polytechnics using the stratified sampling techniques. Data gathered were analyzed using frequency tables and simple regression analysis to achieve the objectives of the study. The results showed that cooperative societies significantly affected the well-being of staff of public polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria. Specifically, the sub-variables of the cooperative societies were considered significant in the order of educational loan ($p= 0.000$) and commodity purchase (household asset) ($p= 0.000$). This implies that cooperative societies have an effect on the well-being of staff of public polytechnics in Anambra State. The study concluded that access to educational loans and commodity purchases (household assets) have a significant positive relationship on the well-being of staff of public polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria at a 5% level of significance.

Keywords: Cooperative Societies, Wellbeing, Staff, Educational Loans, Commodity Purchase.

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary period, poverty is heating hard on the lives of billions of people around the world. As a result, many people sense incapable to change their lives Desalegn (2019). Odey, Omang, Agba, & Ogaboh, (2018) stated that most Nigerian employees, work in extreme working conditions that affect their productivity and wellwell-beingey asserted that the situation was even made worse with the meager income they earn which many commentators called starvation wages. Concerted efforts by government and other employers of labour to improve the well-being of workers through improved wages, allowances, and social insurance schemes have not yielded much fruits as a significant number of workers still live below the poverty line. Workers themselves through their unions strive in many ways to improve their welfare. Workers pool their resources to form cooperatives and operate same for the benefit of members (Odey, Omang, & Agba, 2018)

Cooperatives have been used by various economies; socialists, capitalists and mixed systems to improve the economic and social well-being of their citizens over time. In the Sub-Sahara, government of countries like Nigeria has made concerted efforts to encourage the formation of cooperatives through the institution of plans, policies, and programmes for effective production, financing, marketing, and consumption of goods and services (Okoli, 2018). Cooperatives are formed to meet peoples' common requirements. They originated from the leading idea that together, a group of people can achieve goals that none of them could attain alone (Ruhul & Mohammed, 2014 as cited in Desalegn, 2019). By making reserve funds, these cooperatives help to lessen members' burden in searching for immediate cash assistance for the unforeseen expenditures. Benefits gained from cooperatives create lots of impact on the economic conditions of members (Rollieza & Daus-Taruc, 2019).

Access to safe and healthy shelter and basic services is essential to a person's societal physical, psychological, social and economic wellbeing. Meanwhile, substantial proportion of the world's population particularly in developing countries lacks shelter and sanitation [UN-Habitat, 2010]. This can affect man's mental health. Going by the position of World Health Organization (WHO) that mental health signifies a state of wellbeing in which every individual realizes his or her own potential, has the ability to cope with normal stresses of life and work productively and fruitfully as well as being able to make a contribution to his or her community (Lawal, 2021). In most developing economies like Nigeria, as stated in Enemuo & Nwankwo, (2021) "there is no clear record of the contribution of cooperative societies to economic well-being and growth in tertiary institutions due to negligence in data-keeping". Hence, the importance of cooperatives is beginning to be felt because of the persistent poverty among low-income earners (Ringim & Shaib, 2017). The strategy for tackling this menace is said to consist of the improvement of the quality of life of the poor through the provision of social services, such as housing, health care, education and public utilities and essential commodities (Yusuf, 2008). Taiwo, Agbasi, Udunze & Okafor, 2014 (as cited in Enemuo & Nwankwo, 2021) asserted "that there is a growing call for the enhancement of the income and all-around socio-economic satisfaction of cooperative members. This is believed to be part of the reason for the organization of cooperative societies as to use their potentials and resources towards the optimal satisfaction of their member's wellbeing". This benefit which may be derived from cooperatives helps to influence members' well-being (Enemuo & Nwankwo, 2021). It is against this background that this study examines the effect of cooperative on wellbeing of staff of public polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEMS

The Nigerian employees are paid salaries that makes them poverty-stricken, broke, bankrupt, penniless, beggars, displaced, and reduced (Agba & Ushie, 2014 as cited in Odey et al., 2018). Most of the staff of Nigerian polytechnics complain of haphazard payment of salaries, non-payment of several months half salary arrears and issues of notional promotions for several years and staff of public polytechnics in Anambra state are not exempted. This significantly affects their spending and welfare. An average Nigeria worker spend less than one dollar a day. Consequently, a vast majority of workers cannot save under conventional commercial bank system or collect loans (Odey et al., 2018).

It is difficult for the staff of Nigerian polytechnics to meet up with their basic needs such as educational, essential commodity and shelter. Cognizant of the financial needs of the employees in the academia, the staffs have engaged in the establishment of cooperatives to encourage thrift and savings mobilization among members for capital formation. It is based on this that the researcher decided to investigate the role cooperative society play on staff wellbeing in public polytechnics in Anambra state. Specifically, the study seeks to examine:

- i. To investigate the effects of educational loan on the well-being of staff of public polytechnic in Anambra state, Nigeria;
- ii. To determine the effect of commodity purchase (household Asset) on the well-being of staff of public polytechnics in Anambra state, Nigeria

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Framework

This work will be anchored on Collective Action Theory as it seems more suitable as demonstrated below. The Collective Action theory was propounded by Mancur Olson in 1965. Uzonwane (2015) reported that the theory states that “individuals under certain institutional arrangements and shared norms are capable of organizing and sustaining cooperation that advances the common interest of the group in which they belong.” This means that individuals can organize and govern themselves to attain benefits which may not be individualized but which benefit the entire group. The theory is applied widely to groups, organizations, agencies, as well as community action. Olson saw collective action as a voluntary action taken by a group to achieve the perceived common needs of members which helps in reducing the challenges of the group

Conceptualization of the Variable

Concept of Cooperative

Cooperatives are voluntary societies owned, managed and democratically controlled by members within a particular location (Adedayo & Yusuf, 2004). Henry and Schimmel posit that it is an independent association of people who willingly come together to establish a jointly owned and democratically controlled enterprise referred to as cooperative to service the diverse needs of its members. It can also be seen as a system designed to enhance the numerous individuals and improve micro and small-scale entrepreneurs both in the rural and urban areas organizing savings and giving access to funds as loans as at when required from the scheme. They are privately established societies of individuals who have agreed to unite and operate a savings and loan system amongst their members (Oluyombo, 2010 as cited in Ajayi, Dada & Folorunso, 2021). ICA (1995) defined a cooperatives as an association of persons, united voluntarily to meet their common economic, social and cultural needs and aspirations through a jointly owned and democratically controlled enterprises. Gabriel, (2023) viewed cooperatives as associations or organizations whose goals are to satisfy their members social, economic and cultural needs.

Onugu & Nwankwo, (2013) as cited in Nwankwo, Ogbodo, & Ewuim, (2016) indicated that in any community, cooperation usually exists in the form of associations of people who come together as a group driven by their social and economic needs in order to cope with their problems and improve their conditions of living. In pursuance of satisfying the socio-economic needs of their members, different types of cooperative societies have emerged, such as:

Consumer Cooperative Societies: This type of cooperative end the chain of production. Goods are bought from the co-operators on a wholesale basis, stored and sold to the consumers and members of the public at the current market price. At a given time, members are paid dividends calculated on the basis of their purchase.

Producer Cooperative Societies: producer cooperatives were formed to enhance the production of goods and services of various kinds. Indeed, the chief characteristic of producer cooperative society is its pronounced cooperative nexus. By this it means a strong functioning working relationship between the cooperative complex and the members. There is a very strong working relationship between a productive society and its members. Ijere, (as cited in Nwankwo, et al., 2016). classified producer cooperative in two: producer cooperatives for mutual work in the area of farming, livestock, fishing, forestry extraction (or mining), processing, industry, labour and handicrafts; and auxiliary cooperative for the marketing of product and the supply of professional goods, such as credit machinery, tools, input, storage, irrigation, accounting, insurance, technical guidance, etc.

Marketing Cooperatives: It is through the marketing cooperatives that the middlemen are eliminated and the unnecessary waste of products avoided. Oraeke (1986) noted that in the villages of old Anambra and Anambra States, for instance, piles of uncracked palm kernels are now left under sun and rain to waste away. If the owners were in marketing cooperatives, it would have been simple for them to dispose of.

Housing Cooperative: This emerged as a result of the system whereby people form a group for the purpose of building houses for one another on rotational basis. As at the time, this type of cooperative existed. Mud and that were used in building.

Transport Cooperative Societies: Transport cooperative societies cater for the transit problems of their members as well as the external transportation of their goods. Sometimes, they carry out some activities for non-members for a price.

Input Service Cooperatives: These societies exist to supply its members with seasoned inputs at reasonable costs. It is mostly operated on an agro-business line.

Cooperative Thrift and Loan Societies: The Roman Catholic teachers in Abeokuta started the first cooperative thrift and loan society in 1940. This type of society was designed for salary earners and primarily to take care of their old age and retirement. Members make regular thrift savings during the period they are under employment and an individual could also make other savings for special purposes if he wishes. Such savings could be children's school fees, vacation, leave, etc.

Concept of Well-being

Well-being has been defined as the combination of feeling good and functioning well; the experience of positive emotions such as happiness and contentment as well as the development of one's potential, having some control over one's life, having a sense of purpose, and experiencing positive relationships (Huppert, 2009 as cited in Ruggeri, Eduardo, Garcia-Garzon, Áine, Matz & Huppert, 2020). It is a sustainable condition that allows the individual or population to develop and thrive. The term subjective well-being is synonymous with positive mental health. The World Health Organization defined positive mental health as "a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community". This conceptualization of well-being goes beyond the absence of mental ill health, encompassing the perception that life is going well.

There are two major approaches to conceptualizing well-being (Ryan & Deci, 2001 as cited in Tov, 2018). The first approach emphasizes a person's evaluation of their own life both emotionally and cognitively. It has been referred to as hedonic well-being (HWB) and consists of (i) frequent pleasant feelings, (ii) infrequent unpleasant feelings, and (iii) an overall judgment that life is satisfying. This tripartite model is also referred to as subjective well-being (Diener, 1984) because it prioritizes a person's own assessment of how well their life is going and whether they are getting the things they want in life--without specific concern for what these "things" actually are. The second approach includes several concepts that together have been referred to as eudemonic well-being (EWB). This approach takes as its starting point that there are certain needs or qualities that are essential for one's psychological growth and development; the fulfillment of these needs enables a person to reach their full potential (Ryan & Deci, 2001 as cited in Tov, 2018).

Empirical Review

Omimakin, Dada, and Omimakinde,(2022) investigated on the impact of cooperative societies on the well-being of the people based on the criteria set which include; ease of access to credit facility, low-interest rate on loans, saving opportunity, educational support, business advice and entrepreneurial training, social activities support and motivation for fixed assets acquisitions and poverty reduction. Questionnaires which was structured on Likert format was distributed to three hundred and sixty respondents who have been purposively selected from members of four(4) cooperative societies in Ile Ife based on ease of accessibility(360).Data collected from the three hundred and twenty(320) respondents who properly completed the questionnaires were expressed in percentages and then analyzed using chi-square (X²). Majority of the respondents affirm that cooperative societies have strongly improve their well-being.

Rasaki, Olojede, Adeoye, and Emiola, (2021) analyzed the contributions of cooperative societies to the well-being of women in the study area. The study was carried out in Yewa North Local Government Area of Ogun State of South Western Nigeria. Systematic sampling technique was used to select 180 respondents from registered members of cooperative societies. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The results revealed that majority (82.22%) of the respondents were married with average age of 53 years. Most of them (99.44%) have formal education with average years of schooling of 11 years and mean household size of 6 members. It was generally affirmed by the respondents that benefits derived from cooperative societies are; access to

credits, training, information and farm input, market for farm produce and social recognition. Majority of the respondents were able to possess farmland, building, motorcycle, bicycle, telephone, radio and television after they joined cooperative societies. They also have better access to good health care and food. The result of t-test showed that there is significant difference in the average monthly income (₦39,614.44 difference) of the women and t-value of 23.64. In conclusion, this study provided strong evidence that cooperative societies contributed a lot to the well-being of women in the study area.

Lawal, (2021) conducted a study on how cooperative societies enhance general well-being through housing provision and services in Nigeria. A total of 330 respondents took part in the study. Questionnaires and interviews were utilized to collect data for the study. The findings revealed that all the cooperative societies ran multipurpose services with housing loan services being equally included. These services included mass purchasing of land (b) acquisition of fixed assets (c) housing loans to members who are about to complete their personal houses or in the process of having one. Cooperative societies were seen as the easiest channels of securing access to affordable housing due to the absence of bureaucratic bottlenecks and insurmountable conditions. The general feeling was that decision-making on how, when, and to whom the loan should be given was faster, reliable, and enhancing social, mental, and physical stability for better productivity

Ajayi and Chilokwu, (2021) carried out a study to examine the effect of cooperative societies on the well-being of staff among Universities in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to access the effects of educational loans on the well-being of the staff, investigate the effect of land acquisition on the well-being of the staff and determine the effect of commodity purchase (household Asset) on the well-being of staff among Universities in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The total population of this study is three thousand two hundred and five (3,205) comprising the entire cooperators in the three Universities in Ekiti State, namely Federal University, Oye Ekiti, Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti, and Afe Babalola University, Ado Ekiti. The study employed a stratified random sampling technique for selecting a sample size of 355 respondents which are further divided among cooperators in the three Universities in Ekiti State. Data gathered were analyzed using frequency tables and multiple regression analysis to achieve the objectives of the study. The results showed that cooperative societies significantly affect the well-being of staff among Universities in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Specifically, the sub-variables of the cooperative societies were considered significant in the order of educational loan ($p= 0.000$), land acquisition ($p= 0.000$) and commodity purchase (household asset) ($p= 0.000$). This implies that cooperative societies have an effect on the well-being of staff among Universities in Ekiti State. The study concluded that access to educational loans, land acquisition, and commodity purchases (household assets) have a significant positive relationship with the well-being of staff among Universities in Ekiti State, Nigeria at a 5% level of significance.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a survey design for more precise investigation because of its ability to provide information on large groups of people with little effort. The area of the Study is Anambra State, Nigeria. Anambra State is one of the five states in the south east, geopolitical zones of Nigeria, Anambra State.

The population of the study is three thousand four hundred and fifty-eight (3,458), which makes up the membership strength of the selected cooperators from the two public polytechnics in Anambra state, namely Federal Polytechnic, Oko and Anambra state Polytechnic, Mgbakwu.

The source of data was primary (structured question) and secondary. The instrument was subject to both validity and reliability test, which came out good (Cronbach alpha value =.87 for reliability) The data was analyzed using frequency tables and Simple Regression model at 0.05 probability level of significance through the aid of SPSS version 23.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Test of Hypothesis

Ho₁: Educational loans do not have a statistically significant effect on the well-being of staff of Public Polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria;

The respondents' scores on two variables of educational loan and wellbeing of staff of Public Polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria; were computed and subjected to simple regression analysis. From Table 1, the R (correlation Coefficient) gives a positive value of 0.944; this indicates that there is a strong and positive relationship between educational loans and the well-being of Staff of Public Polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria; The R² is a portion of the total variation in the dependent variable that is explained by the variation in the independent variables. From the results obtained, R² is equal to 0.863, this implies that educational loan 86.3% variance in the well-being of the staff, this is further proven by the adjusted R² that shows the goodness of fit of the model which gives a value of 0.863, implying that when all errors are corrected and adjustments are made, the model can only account for 86.3% by the educational loan; while the remaining 13.7% are explained by the error term in the model in the surveyed of Public Polytechnics in Anambra State, as shown in Table 1.

The unstandardized beta co-efficient of educational loan is 0.826 with t= 38.132 and (p= 0.000 < 0.05). These results showed that educational loans have an effect on the well-being of staff of Public Polytechnics in Anambra State. This implies that the cooperative institution accepts monthly contributions from members placing them at an advantage when requesting for educational loan.

Table 1: Educational Loan and Well-being of Staff

Variable	Coeff	. Std Error	t-value	Sig.
Constant	0.672	0.093	7.254	0.000
Educational Loan	0.826	0.022	38.132	0.000
R	0.944			

R Square	0.863			
Adj. R Square	0.863			
F Stat.	1454.015(0.000)			

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Ho₂: Commodity purchase (household asset) do not have a significant effect on the well-being of staff of Public Polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria.

The respondents' scores on two variables of commodity purchase and the well-being of staff Public Polytechnics in Anambra State were computed and subjected to simple regression analysis. From Table 2, the R (correlation Coefficient) gives a positive value of 0.914; this indicates that there is a strong and positive relationship between community purchase and the well-being of staff Public Polytechnics in Anambra State. The R² is a portion of the total variation in the dependent variable that is explained by the variation in the independent variables. From the results obtained, R² is equal to 0.833, this implies that commodity purchase brought about 83.3% variance in the well-being of staff, this is further proven by the adjusted R² that shows the goodness of fit of the model which gives a value of 0.832, implying that when all errors are corrected and adjustments are made, the model can only account for 83.2% by commodity purchase; while the remaining 16.8% are explained by the error term in the model in the surveyed of Public Polytechnics in Anambra stat as shown in Table 2.

The unstandardized beta co-efficient of community purchase is 0.795 with t= 31.979 and (p= 0.000 < 0.05). These results showed that commodity purchase has a positive relationship with the well-being of the staff. This suggests that the interest rate charged by cooperative societies on commodities purchased is easily affordable compared to other financial institutions.

Table 4.2: Commodity Purchase and Wellbeing of Staff of Public Polytechnics in Anambra State

Variable	Coeff.	Std Error	t-value.	Sig.
Constant	0.744	0.108	6.879	0.000
Community Purchase	0.795	0.025	31.979	0.000
R	0.914			
R Square	0.833			
Adj. R Square	0.832			

F Stat.	1022.648(0.000)			
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Source: Field Survey, 2023

Summary

From the discussion in objective one, and by p-value $<.05$;

i it showed that the null hypothesis i.e educational loan does not significantly affect the well-being of staff of Public Polytechnics in Anambra state, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. Based on this, we accepted the alternate hypothesis that educational loan affects the well-being of staff of Public Polytechnics in Anambra state.

ii In objective two, the alternative hypothesis was accepted. That is, commodity purchases would significantly affect the well-being of staff of Public Polytechnics state, Nigeria.

CONCLUSIONS

This research was able to appraise the role of cooperative society on staff's well-being in public polytechnics in Anambra state using four selected cooperatives as case study. The research work revealed that cooperative is an instrument to economic freedom in Anambra state, Nigeria. Cooperative impact saving culture on members, and provide easy and unhindered access to micro-credit thereby not only making personal development a reality but also contributing effectively to the wellbeing of the entire population. Cooperative assists members directly and indirectly (cash or kind) in acquiring assets. Acquisition of various assets like electronics, automobiles, landed property and buildings among others had been made possible through the assistance of cooperative society. This had assisted individual members in meeting their physiological and safety needs and bring about improvement in the economic condition of the people.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the above findings and conclusions, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Members should be enlightened on the use of credit and also on the sources from which they can obtain loans and the terms of the available loans.
- ii. Cooperative societies should continually provide demand-driven services to create more opportunities for the members of the cooperatives.
- iii. Members and non-members should be encouraged to patronize cooperatives' products and services to realize more income.

- iv. Tertiary institutions should, as a matter of urgency and priority, review the cooperative society laws and regulations of the university from time to time in order to meet the desired needs and aspirations of the cooperatives.
- v. It is also recommended that cooperative society activities should be properly regulated by government so that it will continue to impact positively on the well-being of its members.

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